

Effects of the energy price crisis on European
households

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Technical Appendix
Version 1.2

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1 Introduction

This Technical Appendix provides further background to the study *Effects of the energy price crisis on European households* (online here). We lay out methodological details including information on data sources, and critically discuss the limitations of this study. In addition, we present extensive additional analyses on the country-level and supplementary results.

2 Method and Discussion

The study *Effects of the energy price crisis on European households* assesses the distributional effects of energy price increases on European households. Its main results follow from an analysis of multi-regional input-output data, household-level expenditure data and scenarios of fuel price increases.

The general idea is that higher energy prices would increase household expenditures if households sustain their consumption levels. The magnitude of expected additional costs reflects country- and industry-specific dependencies on fuels (e.g. what is the share of coal capacity in the electricity sector?), household-specific consumption patterns (e.g. how much does one household spend on natural gas?) and country-specific tax regimes (e.g. to what extent do gasoline price increases reflect wholesale price increases for crude oil?). With rising prices for fossil fuels, households are likely to expect higher additional costs (relative to total expenditures), if consumption goods and services are more fuel-intensive than in other countries, if they spend a larger share on fossil fuels or if they live in countries with relatively lower taxes and levies on fossil fuels. Our modeling approach reflects these properties.

In the following, we describe data and methods as well as important methodological limitations.

2.1 Multi-Regional Input-Output Data

Energy price changes affect households directly (e.g. through increased costs for purchasing gas for heating or gasoline for transportation), but also indirectly through increased (production) costs for goods and services. In our model, we include both, direct and indirect cost effects. Direct additional costs reflect household-specific consumption patterns of fossil fuels. Indirect additional costs reflect household-specific consumption patterns of households, but also within-economy supply chain linkages. Households, which consume goods and services that require more fossil fuels along their value chain, are likely to face higher additional indirect costs if energy prices increase.

We study indirect cost effects with the help of multi-regional input-output (MRIO) data. MRIO-data describes monetary flows across regions and sectors and thus allows determining each sector's dependency on specific inputs (including energy) in each region. The MRIO-data includes an inter-industry flow matrix $Z \in \mathbb{R}^{(m \cdot n) \cdot (m \cdot n)}$ with n regions and m sectors. Each $z_{r_i s_i}^{r_j s_j}$ of Z with $r_i, r_j \in \{1, \dots, n\}$ and $s_i, s_j \in \{1, \dots, m\}$ represent total monetary value (in USD) flowing from sector s_i in region r_i to sector s_j in region r_j . Entries of Z do not include value-added tax. Vector $Y \in \mathbb{R}^{(m \cdot n) \cdot (n)}$ comprises the final demand in each region n . Each $y_{r_i s_i}^{r_j}$ of Y denotes the aggregate monetary value flowing from sector s_i in region r_i into final demand in region r_j .

We subsequently calculate the technology matrix $A \in \mathbb{R}^{(m \cdot n) \cdot (m \cdot n)}$ with entries $a_{r_i s_i}^{r_j s_j}$.

$$a_{r_i s_i}^{r_j s_j} = \frac{z_{r_i s_i}^{r_j s_j}}{\sum_s \sum_r z_{r_j s_j}^{rs} + \sum_r y_{r_j s_j}^r} \quad (1)$$

Each $a_{r_i s_i}^{r_j s_j}$ denotes the value (in USD) of each input from sector s_i in region r_i to produce one USD of output from sector s_j in region r_j . We next derive the Leontief inverse L , which includes pre-products along the value chain. I denotes the identity matrix.

$$L = (I - A)^{-1} \quad (2)$$

We are interested in the indirect cost effects of price increases for natural gas, crude oil and coal. We therefore create a vector $F^f \in \mathbb{R}^{(m \cdot n)}$, which denotes $F_{r, s_i}^f = 1$, if s_i represents the sector f of natural gas, oil or coal production, and $F_{r, s_j}^f = 0$ otherwise. We proceed by calculating $c_{r_i s_i}^f$ as follows:

$$c_{r_i s_i}^f = \sum_{r_j} \sum_{s_j} L_{r_j s_j}^{r_i s_i} \cdot F_{r_j s_j}^f \quad (3)$$

$c_{r_i s_i}$ denotes the total indirect costs on natural gas, oil or coal in USD, which is embedded in one USD of output in each sector s_i in region r_i . We allow for fuel-specific price changes by calculating $c_{r_i s_i}^f$ with $f \in (gas, oil, coal)$ separately. $c_{r^* s^*}^{oil}$ is relatively high, if the production process of sector s^* in region r^* is relatively oil-intensive or if producing one unit of output from sector s^* in region r^* requires inputs from other regions r^+ and sectors s^+ , in which production is relatively oil-intensive.

We use data from the GTAP database (Aguilar et al. 2019). The GTAP database includes trade data for 65 sectors ($m = 65$) in 141 countries ($n = 141$) reflecting production processes and trade relationships from 2014. We convert this trade data into a multi-regional input-output table (Peters et al. 2011). See Steckel et al. (2021) for further details in a similar application of this method.

2.2 Household Budget Data

Energy price changes affect households differently, depending on the energy intensity of each household's consumption. The energy intensity of each household's consumption comprises the energy intensity of each good or service consumed by the household. The consumption of fossil fuels (such as natural gas for heating or gasoline for transportation) will incur direct additional costs if fossil fuel prices increase. The consumption of non-energy items, such as food or services, will lead to indirect additional costs when fuel prices increase. The magnitude of these additional costs depends on the fossil fuels used as inputs along the value chains.

We use data from the Household Budget Survey (HBS) 2015 from Eurostat (2015). It includes socio-demographic data as well as highly disaggregated data on yearly consumption expenditures at the household-level. The data is representative at the country-level and covers information on 264,604 households from 24 countries in Europe. Specifically, it covers all EU member states, except for Austria, Malta and Slovenia.

We perform multiple cleaning steps. In a first step, we identify and remove duplicates of households based on socio-demographic information and item-level expenditures. In total, we remove 457 households from our sample. Second, we winsorize item-level expenditures for each country at the 99th percentile and replace it with the country-level

median of all non-zero expenditures. Third, we convert yearly expenditure data to prices of 2014, since data from the MRIO-model expresses inter-industry linkages of 2014.

For within-country analyses, we bin households to country-level expenditure quintiles based on total household expenditures per capita. The first expenditure quintile comprises those 20% of households with the lowest expenditures per capita. For across-country analyses, we bin households to Europe-level expenditure quintiles based on total expenditures per capita, adjusted for purchasing power parity (PPP).

For each household, we compute item-level expenditure shares (e.g. how much does each household spend on electricity in percent of total expenditures). We also compute expenditure shares for each consumption sector $s_i \in \{1, \dots, m\}$ and consumption category. Consumption categories comprise expenditures on district heating, gas heating, oil heating, transport fuels (such as diesel and gasoline), electricity, food, goods, services and other energy (such as LPG). The dataset, which we will use in this analysis, thus reflects household-specific consumption patterns (as of 2015).

We are unable to learn about each household's heating type from survey data. Instead, we use non-zero expenditures on natural gas for heating (item code 04521), district heating (item code 04550) or liquid heating fuels (item code 04530) as an indicator. Data on the number of gas users from our study might thus not accurately reflect the actual number of households heating with gas.

One important extension applies to the expenditure data of German households, where disaggregated expenditure information on residential energy consumption is missing. Instead, German households only report aggregate expenditures on housing and energy (item code 04). This hinders a granular simulation of additional costs in German households. Therefore, we impute household-level expenditures on electricity, natural gas or heating with the help of data from *Einkommens- und Verbrausstichprobe* (EVS) 2018. Access to EVS is strictly confidential, which restricts our ability to directly draw on EVS data for simulation purposes. We use percentile-average expenditure shares of natural gas, electricity and heating energy to compute the total expenditures on those energy items. Therefore, household-level expenditures on energy items in German households express total household-level expenditures on housing and residential energy (from HBS 2015), but percentile-level expenditure shares (from EVS 2018). This includes that virtually all households in Germany (97%) report non-zero expenditures on natural gas, which restricts the possibility of credibly assessing the share of households heating with natural gas.

2.3 Fossil Fuel Price Scenarios

For our analysis, we create three different scenarios, namely the 'baseline scenario', the 'embargo scenario' and the 'stylized scenario'. While the 'stylized scenario' assumes that direct and indirect costs double, we consider for the two other scenarios that country- and fuel-specific changes in wholesale market prices will affect consumer prices both, directly and indirectly, but differently, depending on country-specific tax regimes. In the following, we outline the assumptions and methods to translate changes in wholesale market prices into consumer prices.

2.3.1 Natural Gas

Our simulation approach requires modeling how higher wholesale gas prices would affect retail gas prices. This is not straightforward. Retail prices differ between each country,

within each country between household and non-household consumers, within these groups depending on the amount of consumed gas, and ultimately on individual contracts.

For our analysis, we approximate higher average retail prices i) for each country and ii) for the two consumer groups households and non-households. We thus neglect price differences depending on consumed gas quantities or individual contracts. The general idea of our approach is to multiply the market price component, i.e. the retail price without taxes, with a markup factor that reflects the wholesale price increase in our scenarios compared to a historical average.

We use data from the Natural gas price statistics from Eurostat (2022b). The annual Eurostat data is available for all EU countries and distinguishes between eight price components, namely 1) energy and supply, 2) network costs, and 3) taxes, fees, levies and charges. Component 3) comprises the 4) value added tax (VAT), 5) renewable taxes, 6) capacity taxes, 7) environmental taxes, and 8) other (for more information see Eurostat (2022a)).

We first calculate the markup factor. The ‘baseline scenario’ assumes a wholesale gas price of 125 EUR/MWh, while we select 25 EUR/MWh as a historical average. For this scenario, the markup factor is 5. We calculate retail prices for households in four steps:

1. We multiply the historical energy and supply prices averaged over the years 2017-2021 with the markup factor to obtain the markup energy price before taxes.
2. We then add network costs and all taxes, fees, levies and charges, except for the VAT.
3. We add the VAT to the price calculated in step 2 using country-specific VAT rates for the year 2021.
4. We finally calculate the percentage change increases of the marked-up price compared to the historical household gas prices.

The calculation for non-households is analogous, except that we follow the Eurostat convention by exclusively focusing on non-refundable price components, which excludes the VAT. Step 3 is thus obsolete.

Formula 4 denotes the calculation.

$$p_{s^*} = ((p_h^0 \cdot \pi) + \eta)(1 + \tau) \quad (4)$$

p_{s^*} describes the price in our scenario. p_h^w describes historical retail price excluding taxes and levies. π refers to the markup factor, η to network costs, taxes, fees, levies and charges, except VAT. We denote the VAT rate with τ . We next derive the relative price increase as follows:

$$\lambda^* = \frac{(p_{s^*}^* - p_h^*)}{p_h^*} \quad (5)$$

λ^* expresses the relative change of retail prices under wholesale price increases as in our scenarios ($p_{s^*}^*$) compared to historical average retail prices p_h^* . For this study, we list λ^* in columns 4-7 in Table 1.

Eurostat data is unavailable for household-level gas prices in Cyprus and Finland and unavailable for non-household-level gas prices in Cyprus. Figure A1 in the main text provides some intuition about the potential impact of different fuels - natural gas accounts for a low share of gross available energy in those countries. As a workaround, we impute the mean across all European countries for missing changes in retail prices.

Table 1: Natural gas prices: historical prices and increases for baseline and embargo scenario

Country	Price in EUR/MWh		Price increase (%)			
	Historical average (2017-2021)		Baseline scenario		Embargo scenario	
	Households	Non-households	Households	Non-households	Households	Non-households
Belgium	0.056	0.026	209%	291%	431%	599%
Bulgaria	0.043	0.026	219%	288%	449%	592%
Czechia	0.061	0.029	272%	265%	563%	545%
Denmark	0.088	0.041	123%	199%	254%	409%
Germany	0.062	0.033	189%	215%	390%	443%
Estonia	0.045	0.035	239%	236%	491%	486%
Ireland	0.068	0.032	182%	205%	374%	422%
Greece	0.062	0.034	190%	254%	396%	522%
Spain	0.082	0.028	152%	254%	312%	524%
France	0.077	0.036	165%	225%	340%	462%
Croatia	0.038	0.032	244%	271%	502%	558%
Italy	0.078	0.034	172%	242%	358%	498%
Latvia	0.044	0.029	185%	247%	381%	508%
Lithuania	0.042	0.032	194%	248%	400%	510%
Luxembourg	0.044	0.028	206%	281%	425%	579%
Hungary	0.033	0.027	227%	282%	468%	580%
Netherlands	0.092	0.036	139%	204%	285%	420%
Austria	0.068	0.031	185%	237%	381%	487%
Poland	0.046	0.032	226%	266%	465%	548%
Portugal	0.090	0.027	156%	286%	322%	589%
Romania	0.033	0.028	241%	271%	497%	558%
Slovakia	0.046	0.032	195%	246%	402%	507%
Sweden	0.139	0.049	146%	162%	301%	335%

2.3.2 Oil

Similar to natural gas, we know that prices for all petroleum products differ between countries, especially due to different taxes and levies. We obtain price increases for our scenario by approximating higher retail prices i) for each country, and ii) for four oil-based products, namely gasoline, diesel, heating oil, and liquefied petroleum gas (LPG). We follow a similar methodology as for the gas price increase, i.e. by multiplying the prices of all products per country before taxes with a specific markup factor, and then adding energy taxes and the VAT (see steps 1-4 in the previous section).

We use data from the Weekly Oil bulletin from Eurostat (2022c), and more specifically ‘Prices over time’ from 2005 onwards. The weekly data is available for all EU countries. We use time-series data until 11.04.22 for prices with and without taxes as well as country specific VATs. We first define the historical crude oil price (Brent) of 60 USD/bbl. For our ‘baseline scenario’, we assume a crude oil price (Brent) of 110 USD/bbl. With a historic average price of 60 USD/bbl, we obtain a price increase π of roughly 83%. The country-specific historical prices for the four petroleum products are, as for natural gas, the mean prices between 2017-2021. Table 2 (Table 3) shows the resulting price markups λ_{fuel}^* for each country by fuel type in the ‘baseline scenario’ (‘embargo scenario’).

2.3.3 Coal

We use a simplified method to calculate the coal price increase compared to natural gas and oil. In our model, we assume that a wholesale price increase for hard coal directly affects input prices for consumers, applies to all types of coal, similarly across countries, and for all consumer groups.

We thereby neglect that coal used directly by households may differ in prices. While hard coal is traded internationally and prices have increased since the beginning of the Ukraine war, lignite is usually mined and consumed domestically and prices are deter-

Table 2: Petroleum price increases, ‘baseline scenario’

Country	Gasoline	Diesel	Heating oil	LPG
Belgium	38%	40%	80%	83%
Bulgaria	47%	52%	50%	46%
Cyprus	45%	48%	70%	-
Czech Republic	41%	47%	70%	68%
Germany	37%	45%	74%	68%
Denmark	33%	40%	45%	-
Estonia	42%	45%	74%	54%
Spain	46%	51%	70%	78%
Finland	36%	47%	57%	-
France	36%	39%	66%	70%
Greece	35%	50%	-	-
Croatia	44%	48%	84%	80%
Hungary	38%	40%	40%	53%
Ireland	38%	43%	57%	-
Italy	35%	39%	50%	60%
Lithuania	45%	51%	80%	53%
Luxembourg	44%	51%	82%	73%
Latvia	43%	49%	77%	57%
Netherlands	33%	44%	35%	54%
Poland	41%	45%	61%	53%
Portugal	31%	37%	50%	48%
Romania	43%	54%	47%	51%
Sweden	38%	50%	46%	-
Slovak Republic	40%	49%	-	66%

The table shows the price increase of our ‘baseline scenario’ for gasoline (2), diesel (3), heating oil (4), and LPG (5).

mined via long-term contracts. Changes in hard coal prices are therefore unlikely to affect prices of lignite. We thus likely overestimate the impact of coal.

For our ‘baseline scenario’, we use a price level of 250 USD/t, while taking a price level of 100 USD/t as a reference. We hence assume an increase of the wholesale price λ_{coal}^* of 150%. Table 3 in the main document contains the price assumptions of all three scenarios.

2.4 Calculation of Additional Costs

Total additional costs to households following price increases as specified in our scenarios reflect direct and indirect cost effects. For each household k in country r , we match item-level expenditure data and country-sector-level data from multi-regional input-output modeling and consequently derive the additional costs ac_k^r for a price increase of each fuel $f \in \{gas, oil, coal\}$ as follows:

$$ac_k^{rf} = \sum_s (exp_{sk} \cdot c_{rs}^f \cdot \lambda_{f1}^* + exp_{sk} \cdot c_{dir} \cdot \lambda_{f2}^*) \quad (6)$$

The first summand expresses the indirect additional costs. The second summand expresses the direct additional costs. For natural gas, λ_{f1}^* expresses gas price increases for non-household consumers, while λ_{f2}^* refers to gas price increases for household consumers. c_{dir} equals 1 for each direct energy consumption item (such as natural gas, heating oil, transport fuels) and zero otherwise. For oil, λ_{f1}^* is an average across all different final products (gasoline, diesel, heating oil, LPG), for which we model differing price increases λ_{f2}^* . For coal, λ_{f1}^* equals λ_{f2}^* . We use exp_{sk} from household budget data as described in Section 2.2 and c_{rs}^f for each fuel $f \in \{gas, oil, coal\}$ as described in Section 2.1.

Consequently, total additional costs for each household k in each scenario are the

Table 3: Petroleum price increases, ‘embargo scenario’

Country	Gasoline	Diesel	Heating oil	LPG
Belgium	61%	64%	128%	133%
Bulgaria	75%	83%	81%	73%
Cyprus	71%	76%	111%	-
Czech Republic	66%	75%	111%	108%
Germany	59%	72%	118%	109%
Denmark	53%	63%	71%	-
Estonia	67%	72%	119%	87%
Spain	73%	81%	111%	125%
Finland	58%	75%	91%	-
France	57%	63%	105%	112%
Greece	57%	80%	-	-
Croatia	71%	77%	134%	128%
Hungary	60%	65%	65%	85%
Ireland	60%	69%	92%	-
Italy	56%	62%	80%	96%
Lithuania	72%	81%	127%	85%
Luxembourg	71%	82%	130%	117%
Latvia	69%	78%	123%	91%
Netherlands	53%	70%	56%	86%
Poland	66%	72%	98%	85%
Portugal	49%	59%	80%	77%
Romania	68%	86%	75%	81%
Sweden	60%	80%	74%	-
Slovak Republic	65%	78%	-	106%

The table shows the price increase of our ‘embargo scenario’ for gasoline (2), diesel (3), heating oil (4), and LPG (5).

sum of direct and indirect costs for increases of natural gas, oil and coal. To facilitate comparison between households, we express the total additional costs as a share of total household expenditures (in percent). This is the variable of interest in this study.

$$AC_k = \frac{ac_k^{gas} + ac_k^{oil} + ac_k^{coal}}{\sum_s exp_{sk}} \quad (7)$$

AC_k captures how much of its entire expenditure budget each household k would have to spend *in addition* to current total expenditures to consume the same amount of goods and services, provided they would observe price increases for natural gas, oil and coal, as specified. Any households, for which we calculate additional costs of $AC_k = 1\%$, would require an additional 1% of current total expenditures to acquire the same amount of goods and services given rising prices for natural gas, oil and coal as before.

Next, we model different compensation schemes. Modeled transfers for the compensation scheme ‘Poor households, only gas’ equal the country-level average of total additional costs among the poorest 40% of households resulting from the direct consumption of natural gas, i.e. we disregard direct cost effects from rising prices for oil and coal as well as all indirect effects. Households are eligible for this transfer if they find themselves among the poorest 40% of a country and report non-zero expenditures on natural gas or district heat.

Modeled transfers from the compensation scheme ‘All households, only gas’ equal the country-level average of total additional costs resulting from the direct consumption of natural gas, i.e. we disregard direct cost effects from rising prices for oil and coal as well as all indirect effects. Each household, which reports non-zero expenditures on natural gas or district heat, is eligible for this transfer.

Modeled transfers from the compensation scheme ‘All households, all fuels’ equal the country-level average total additional costs, including direct and indirect cost effects from

rising prices for natural gas, oil and coal. For each compensation scheme, we next compute the net budget change by subtracting expected additional costs ac_k from respective transfers at_k^{scheme} . Again, we express the net budget change ac_k^{scheme} as a share of total household expenditures (in percent). Positive values of ac_k^{scheme} indicate that households would receive transfers, which are higher than expected additional costs. Negative values of ac_k^{scheme} indicate that received transfers would not suffice to fully offset expected additional costs.

2.5 Descriptive Analysis

We provide further supplementary information at the country-level. Figures 1 to 24 display several descriptive analyses for each country drawing on our modeling results.

Panel A) displays the additional costs to households (in % of total expenditures) in the ‘stylized scenario’, i.e. for fuel price increases of 100%. Boxes indicate the 25th to 75th interpercentile range. Ends of whiskers indicate the 5th and 95th percentile, respectively. White rhombes indicate the mean, while green squares indicate the average additional costs following gas price increases. Total additional costs comprise direct and indirect effects.

Panel B) and panel C) show the additional costs to households (in % of total expenditures) in the ‘baseline scenario’ and the ‘embargo scenario’, respectively.

Panel D) displays the additional costs to households (in % of total expenditures) over total household expenditures (in EUR) for each household in the ‘stylized scenario’. The blue curve shows a polynomial regression curve fitted to the data including a 95% confidence interval. Panel E) and panel F) show the additional costs to households (in % of total expenditures) in the ‘baseline scenario’ and the ‘embargo scenario’, respectively.

Panel G) displays average additional costs to households (in % of total expenditures) for each country, expenditure quintile, and consumption category in the ‘stylized scenario’ - only including a price increase for natural gas. Additional costs comprise direct and indirect effects.

Panel J) displays the expenditure share on gas or district heat (in % of total expenditures) over expenditure quintiles. Boxes indicate the 25th to 75th interpercentile range. Ends of whiskers indicate the 5th and 95th percentile, respectively. White rhombes indicate the mean.

Panel K) displays the share of all households per expenditure quintile (in %) which report non-zero expenditures for natural gas (red bar), for heating oil (blue bar), for district heat (yellow bar) or no heating expenditures (green bar.) Note that bars for Germany are unlikely to reflect the distribution of heating sources across the population.

Panel J) displays the expenditure share on different consumption categories (in % of total expenditures) over total household expenditures (in EUR). Curves represent polynomial regression curves fitted to the data including a 95% confidence interval.

2.6 Limitations and Discussion

The interpretation and discussion of our results merit an understanding of several methodological limitations, which we discuss in the following.

First, we use several assumptions on how higher prices for natural gas, oil and coal affect prices observed in households. Specifically, our methodological approach of multiplying the country- and fuel-specific market price components of natural and oil(-based

products) with the percentage increase of wholesale prices implies that wholesale prices are proportional to production costs, which is an assumption. Moreover, we assume that higher prices for wholesale prices are completely passed through to households. We select this method as changes in wholesale prices affect prices for heating fuels with a delay and are not yet visible. Nevertheless, this assumption leads to overstated consumer prices. On the other hand, we do not model price markups at the refinery level, which might even exceed price increases on the wholesale market.

Second, our variable of interest expresses ‘additional overnight costs’, i.e. assumes a completely inelastic demand of households. Our variable of interest can be interpreted as the amount of additional expenditures, which every household would need to sustain current consumption levels - not *actual* additional costs accruing in households. We thereby rule out the substitution of products, i.e. that households change quantities in light of higher prices. There is ample evidence that household demand is sensitive to price changes with demand elasticities differing by consumption item and the magnitude of price changes. Specifically, many households exhibit demand reductions in light of current levels of fuel prices. If we were to assess additional costs, which express more accurately *actual* additional costs in households, we would be likely to observe lower additional costs in households compared to numbers from this study. Nevertheless, lower levels of additional costs would go hand in hand with lower levels of welfare, since households would shift and likely cut consumption.

Third, we do not distinguish between differences in the physical fuel supply dependence of European countries and hence not between different dependencies on natural gas or oil from Russia. We treat fossil fuels imports from different regions similarly in each economy. Supply shortages or restrictions might thus affect wholesale prices in single economies differently, which might lead to different household prices. Implicitly, we assume that all European countries have equal access to available stocks of fossil fuels and that pre-invasion fuel price differences are the only distinctive element between countries. This assumption is critical in the case of natural gas since gas trade often requires fixed physical infrastructure, such as pipelines.

Fourth, we focus on the distributional effects of higher fossil fuel prices and neglect macroeconomic or labor market impacts of existing (or potential) sanctions or fuel supply restrictions. We also do not study increased prices of other goods and services, such as food price increases following supply shortages of wheat. Additional costs in households for food reflect indirect costs incurred through energy used in food production value chains.

Fifth, our analysis does not explicitly consider compensation schemes, which governments have implemented during the last months. Those include - among others - tax reductions, which reduce fuel price increases. In contrast, our analysis describes additional costs of fully uncompensated price increases as a benchmark for uncompensated costs. Modeled compensation schemes in section 4 provide an indication of expected impacts and costs of different, stylized approaches, which are nevertheless grounded on data.

Sixth, our analysis rests on household data from the year 2015 and multi-regional input-output data for 2014. We therefore neglect (possible) changes in consumption behaviour and structural and technological change. Inter-industry flows change only gradually, while specifically in 2014 oil prices were relatively high, between 100-120 USD/bbl. This implies that our model might underestimate indirect additional costs through increasing oil prices since industries are likely to have used more oil in the recent past than

in 2014.

Seventh, the household expenditure data lacks data on installed heating systems and technologies. We thereby infer the type of heating systems from household expenditures. We identify households, which report non-zero expenditures on natural gas, as gas users. Nevertheless, we are agnostic on whether households use gas for heating or cooking. In addition, some households pay for heating via rent payments and occasionally report so in expenditure surveys. This may underestimate additional costs for price increases of heating fuels.

Eighth, some limitations apply to the interpretation of additional costs among German households, as described in section 2.3.1. Most likely, we underestimate the heterogeneity of additional cost burdens among German households. If data was more likely to reflect real circumstances, some German households would face substantially higher additional costs than others would, while others would face substantially lower additional costs. Currently, differences within expenditure quintiles in Germany stem from variations in total expenditure shares on housing and energy compared to total expenditures. For a detailed investigation of the distributional implications of rising energy prices in Germany, please see Kalkuhl et al. (2022).

3 Figures

Figure 1: Supplementary analyses for Belgium

This figure indicates multiple supplementary analyses as described in Section 2.5. Figures are based on household-level expenditure data and multi-regional input-output data.

Figure 2: Supplementary analyses for Bulgaria

This figure indicates multiple supplementary analyses as described in Section 2.5. Figures are based on household-level expenditure data and multi-regional input-output data.

Figure 3: Supplementary analyses for Croatia

This figure indicates multiple supplementary analyses as described in Section 2.5. Figures are based on household-level expenditure data and multi-regional input-output data.

Figure 4: Supplementary analyses for Cyprus

This figure indicates multiple supplementary analyses as described in Section 2.5. Figures are based on household-level expenditure data and multi-regional input-output data.

Figure 5: Supplementary analyses for Czech Republic

This figure indicates multiple supplementary analyses as described in Section 2.5. Figures are based on household-level expenditure data and multi-regional input-output data.

Figure 6: Supplementary analyses for Denmark

This figure indicates multiple supplementary analyses as described in Section 2.5. Figures are based on household-level expenditure data and multi-regional input-output data.

Figure 7: Supplementary analyses for Estonia

This figure indicates multiple supplementary analyses as described in Section 2.5. Figures are based on household-level expenditure data and multi-regional input-output data.

Figure 8: Supplementary analyses for Finland

This figure indicates multiple supplementary analyses as described in Section 2.5. Figures are based on household-level expenditure data and multi-regional input-output data.

Figure 9: Supplementary analyses for France

This figure indicates multiple supplementary analyses as described in Section 2.5. Figures are based on household-level expenditure data and multi-regional input-output data.

Figure 10: Supplementary analyses for Germany

This figure indicates multiple supplementary analyses as described in Section 2.5. Figures are based on household-level expenditure data and multi-regional input-output data.

Figure 11: Supplementary analyses for Greece

This figure indicates multiple supplementary analyses as described in Section 2.5. Figures are based on household-level expenditure data and multi-regional input-output data.

Figure 12: Supplementary analyses for Hungary

This figure indicates multiple supplementary analyses as described in Section 2.5. Figures are based on household-level expenditure data and multi-regional input-output data.

Figure 13: Supplementary analyses for Ireland

This figure indicates multiple supplementary analyses as described in Section 2.5. Figures are based on household-level expenditure data and multi-regional input-output data.

Figure 14: Supplementary analyses for Italy

This figure indicates multiple supplementary analyses as described in Section 2.5. Figures are based on household-level expenditure data and multi-regional input-output data.

Figure 15: Supplementary analyses for Latvia

This figure indicates multiple supplementary analyses as described in Section 2.5. Figures are based on household-level expenditure data and multi-regional input-output data.

Figure 16: Supplementary analyses for Lithuania

This figure indicates multiple supplementary analyses as described in Section 2.5. Figures are based on household-level expenditure data and multi-regional input-output data.

Figure 17: Supplementary analyses for Luxembourg

This figure indicates multiple supplementary analyses as described in Section 2.5. Figures are based on household-level expenditure data and multi-regional input-output data.

Figure 18: Supplementary analyses for Netherlands

This figure indicates multiple supplementary analyses as described in Section 2.5. Figures are based on household-level expenditure data and multi-regional input-output data.

Figure 19: Supplementary analyses for Poland

This figure indicates multiple supplementary analyses as described in Section 2.5. Figures are based on household-level expenditure data and multi-regional input-output data.

Figure 20: Supplementary analyses for Portugal

This figure indicates multiple supplementary analyses as described in Section 2.5. Figures are based on household-level expenditure data and multi-regional input-output data.

Figure 21: Supplementary analyses for Romania

This figure indicates multiple supplementary analyses as described in Section 2.5. Figures are based on household-level expenditure data and multi-regional input-output data.

Figure 22: Supplementary analyses for Slovak Republic

This figure indicates multiple supplementary analyses as described in Section 2.5. Figures are based on household-level expenditure data and multi-regional input-output data.

Figure 23: Supplementary analyses for Spain

This figure indicates multiple supplementary analyses as described in Section 2.5. Figures are based on household-level expenditure data and multi-regional input-output data.

Figure 24: Supplementary analyses for Sweden

This figure indicates multiple supplementary analyses as described in Section 2.5. Figures are based on household-level expenditure data and multi-regional input-output data.

4 Tables

Author	Title	Date	Scenario title	Scenario information	Gas price	Oil price
IFO	ifo Konjunkturprognose, Frühjahr 2022: Folgen des russisch-ukrainischen Krieges dämpfen deutsche Konjunktur	23.03.2022	Base scenario	Only temporary increase of commodity prices, supply shortages, and uncertainty	E.g.: 124 EUR/MWh in 06/22, 100 EUR/MWh in 01/23, 60 EUR/MWh in 06/23	E.g.: 92 EUR/bbl in 06/22, 81 EUR/bbl in 01/23, 78 EUR/bbl in 06/23
IFO	ifo Konjunkturprognose, Frühjahr 2022: Folgen des russisch-ukrainischen Krieges dämpfen deutsche Konjunktur	23.03.2022	Alternative scenario	Intensified situation until mid-2022, before gradual relaxation	E.g.: 195 EUR/MWh in 06/22, 158 EUR/MWh in 01/23, 132 EUR/MWh in 06/23	E.g.: 137 EUR/bbl in 06/22, 119 EUR/bbl in 01/23, 106 EUR/bbl in 06/23
Deutsche Bank Research	Krieg in der Ukraine – Neue Realitäten 2.0	09.03.2022	Moderate scenario		115 EUR/MWh (average 2022)	110 USD/bbl (average 2022)
Deutsche Bank Research	Krieg in der Ukraine – Neue Realitäten 2.0	09.03.2022	More extreme scenario	Considers temporary stop of oil- and gas deliveries from Russia	150 EUR/MWh (average 2022)	140 USD/bbl (average 2022)
IMK	IMK Report Nr. 174, März 2022, Ukraine-Krieg erschwert Erholung nach Pandemie	29.03.2022	Base scenario	Sustained sanctions on Russia, no gas embargo. Moderate increase of energy prices and only short term decline of economic activity	150 EUR/MWh (peak in Q2/22, Ger-many), av-erage 60+ EUR/MWh in 2023	roughly 100 EUR/bbl (mean of Brent, WTI, UAE Dubai in 2022), roughly 90 EUR/bbl (2023)
IMK	IMK Report Nr. 174, März 2022, Ukraine-Krieg erschwert Erholung nach Pandemie	29.03.2022	Risk scenario	Sustained sanctions on Russia, no gas embargo. More intensive and sustained energy price shocks	200 EUR/MWh (peak in Q2/22, Ger-many), av-erage 80+ EUR/MWh in 2023	roughly 140 EUR/bbl (mean of Brent, WTI, UAE Dubai in 2022), roughly 130 EUR/bbl (2023)
IMK	IMK Report Nr. 174, März 2022, Ukraine-Krieg erschwert Erholung nach Pandemie	29.03.2022	Embargo	Gas price result of model, authors care-fully discuss potential caveats	900 EUR/MWh	

Oxford nomics	Eco-	A darker economic scenario from Russia's war	02.03.2022	Downside	War continues until 2023, further sanctions by the west, 6 months of complete gas embargo for Europe	Roughly 60 USD/Mn BTU (204 USD/MWh, 2022). Roughly 45 USD/Mn BTU (average 2023, linear price reduction) Roughly 30 USD/Mn BTU (102 USD/MWh, 2022). Roughly 20 USD/Mn BTU (average 2023, linear price reduction)	115 USD/bbl (peak 2022), above 100bbl (rest of year)
Oxford nomics	Eco-	A darker economic scenario from Russia's war	02.03.2022	Full scale invasion			
Goldman Sachs		Squaring Russia's missing barrels	07.03.2022	Prior case	Accelerated demand-led rebalancing, a pending Iranian nuclear deal, limited disruption to Russian exports		115 USD/bbl (Brent, average 2022), 95 USD/bbl (2023)
Goldman Sachs		Squaring Russia's missing barrels	07.03.2022	Quotas and waivers	Russian exports settle at 2 mb/day lower (consistent with Western self-sanctioning for example)		145 USD/bbl (Brent, average 2022), 125 USD/bbl (2023)
Goldman Sachs		Squaring Russia's missing barrels	07.03.2022	Full blockade	Severe disruptions where exports remain reduced by 4 mb/d (on Western secondary sanctions or Russian self-imposed export restrictions)		175 USD/bbl (Brent, average 2022), 155 USD/bbl (2023)
JP Morgan		What's Next For Oil And Gas Prices As Sanctions On Russia Intensify	10.03.2022	Infrastructure damage	Ukrainian pipelines are damaged, reduction of 30% (33.5 bcm) reduced natural gas flow to Europe. LNG to fill supply gap	180+ EUR/MWh	
JP Morgan		What's Next For Oil And Gas Prices As Sanctions On Russia Intensify	10.03.2022	Total down of gas	Cut down all gas supply (either EU embargo or Russian stop), 120bcm reduction	200+ EUR/MWh (TTF, average 2022)	

JP Morgan	What's Next For Oil And Gas Prices As Sanctions On Russia Intensify	10.03.2022	Disruption of oil continues as now (time of article)	Status quo of 70% of Russian oil without buyers until end 2022	185 USD/bbl (Brent, end 2022)
JP Morgan	What's Next For Oil And Gas Prices As Sanctions On Russia Intensify	10.03.2022	Disruption of oil continues as now (time of article)	Status quo, but several measures options to fill supply gap (higher production by Iran, OPEC and release of Strategic Petroleum Reserve (SPR))	From 110 USD/bbl (Brent) in Q2/22 to 90 USD/bbl in Q4/22
ABN AMRO	Energy Monitor - Energy prices to rise even further if supply disruptions increase	10.03.2022	Base case	Ongoing and strengthened supply reduction for at least one year, self-sanctioning of oil, no reduction in gas flow.	110-130 USD/bbl (Brent), 105-125 USD/bbl (WTI)
ABN AMRO	Energy Monitor - Energy prices to rise even further if supply disruptions increase	10.03.2022	Base case	Ongoing and strengthened supply reduction for at least one year, self-sanctioning of oil, no reduction in gas flow.	110-130 USD/bbl (Brent), 105-125 USD/bbl (WTI)
ABN AMRO	Energy Monitor - Energy prices to rise even further if supply disruptions increase	10.03.2022	Negative scenario	Full supply disruption of Russian oil and gas of up to two years for Europe	130-160 USD/bbl (Brent), 125-155 USD/bbl (WTI)
ABN AMRO	Energy Monitor - Energy prices to rise even further if supply disruptions increase	10.03.2022	Negative scenario	Full supply disruption of Russian oil and gas of up to two years for Europe	130-160 USD/bbl (Brent), 125-155 USD/bbl (WTI)
ABN AMRO	Energy Monitor - Energy prices to rise even further if supply disruptions increase	10.03.2022	Positive scenario	Disruptions of only six months, still some self-sanctioning	80-110 USD/bbl (Brent), 75-105 USD/bbl (WTI)
ABN AMRO	Energy Monitor - Energy prices to rise even further if supply disruptions increase	10.03.2022	Positive scenario	Disruptions of only six months, still some self-sanctioning	80-110 USD/bbl (Brent), 75-105 USD/bbl (WTI)

We have identified these studies via a google search. Parts of the selection is in line with a similar table by German Council of Economic Experts from the 09.04.2022 (see "Table 1" in "A potential sudden stop of energy imports from Russia: Effects on energy security and economic output in Germany and the EU".)

References

- Aguiar, Angel et al. (2019). “The GTAP Data Base: Version 10”. In: *Journal of Global Economic Analysis* 4.1, pp. 1–27.
- Eurostat (2015). *Household Budget Survey 2015*.
- (2022a). *Energy statistics - Gas prices for domestic and industrial consumers*.
- (2022b). *Natural gas price statistics*.
- (2022c). *Weekly Oil Bulletin*.
- Kalkuhl, Matthias et al. (2022). *Effects of the energy price crisis on households in Germany. Socio-political challenges and policy options*.
- Peters, Glen P., Robbie Andrew, and James Lennox (2011). “Constructing an Environmentally-Extended Multi-Regional Input-Output Table Using the GTAP Database”. In: *Economic Systems Research* 23.2, pp. 131–152.
- Steckel, Jan C. et al. (2021). “Distributional impacts of carbon pricing in developing Asia”. In: *Nature Sustainability* 4.11, pp. 1005–1014.